

4-Keto-3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl) Glutaconic Anhydride Arylhydrazones and their Conversion to 2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-3-Carboxyl Acrolein Arylhydrazones

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Since enolizable keto compounds of an aliphatic character having a "reactive methylene group" are known to undergo coupling reactions, various aryldiazonium salts have been coupled with 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride to give coloured compounds which were identified as 4-keto-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride arylhydrazones. These arylhydrazones on alkaline hydrolysis formed corresponding 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-3-carboxyl acrolein arylhydrazones.

Of the many interesting reactions of 3-substituted glutaconic anhydrides, their susceptibility to the attack of an electrophile like diazonium cation is well-known. Thus the addition of aryldiazonium halides to these anhydrides result in the formation of intense-coloured compounds which have been assigned arylhydrazone structure.¹⁻⁴ In the light of these findings it seemed worthwhile to study the coupling of aryldiazonium chloride with 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride which is known to possess an enolic hydroxyl.⁵

Diazotized aromatic amines listed in Table-I were caused to react with equimolar quantity of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride, when bright-coloured compounds were isolated in good yields. The negative ferric chloride colouration test as well as the failure of these compounds to form chelates under variety of conditions⁶⁻⁹ were indicative

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of the absence of enolic hydroxyl at position 5 and, in turn, the absence of an azo structure (I) which may possibly exist in hydrazone form (II). The formation of II can be accounted for on the basis of tautomerism. Additional evidence that these compounds have a hydrazone structure was sought by subjecting them to UV and IR spectral studies. All these compounds are characterized by absorption maxima in the 365-410 $m\mu$ region thereby suggesting the formation of II.^{10,11} None showed maximum at 340 $m\mu$ —the characteristic of azo compounds^{3,4} The IR absorption data for these compounds indicate the distinct absorption at carbonyl stretching frequency, 5.75 and 5.95 μ shifted slightly from the usual position for cyclic anhydride carbonyl. Though shifted, the difference between the two anhydride carbonyl absorption bands 0.20 μ is comparable to that in other anhydrides. The prominent peak at 6.25 μ is attributed to conjugated C-N linkage, while a weak band near 3.2 μ establishes the presence of N-H bending frequency.^{3,4,12-14}

TABLE I

4-Keto-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride arylhydrazones(II) and their characteristics

Sl. No.	Aromatic amine	R	Colour	m. p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
							Found	Required
1.	Aniline	H	Orange	203-205	69	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	8.26	8.52
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	4-CH ₃	Orange	218-220	64	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	8.14	8.33
3.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	2-OCH ₃	Orange	173-175	58	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	7.98	7.95
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisidine	4-OCH ₃	Red	230-232	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	8.06	7.95
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitraniline	2-NO ₂	Yellow	249-250	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	11.40	11.44
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitraniline	3-NO ₂	Yellow	280-282	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	11.58	11.44
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitraniline	4-NO ₂	Brown	291-293	84	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₆	11.52	11.44
8.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	2-Cl	Yellow	228-230	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₄	7.60	7.85
9.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	3-Cl	Yellow	233-235	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₄	7.62	7.85
10.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	4-Cl	Orange	245-247	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₄	7.92	7.85
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	4-Br	Green	238-240	58	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₄	6.69	6.98

Upon alkaline hydrolysis, these arylhydrazones were found to yield monobasic acids of the type IV to the exclusion of expected pyridazone of the type III as reported earlier³. Formation of IV was ascertained through their neutral equivalent, elemental analysis

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and IR spectral determination. The presence of a carboxyl group is obvious by the characteristic broad absorption between $3.35\sim 4\mu$, and a band at 5.85μ , while an appearance of a peak at 3.2μ reveals the presence of NH group.¹⁴ Neither the nitrophenyl nor *p*-bromophenyl-hydrazone undergo such hydrolytic conversion. The physical characteristics of these acids are described in Table-II.

TABLE II

2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-3-carboxyl acrolein arylhydrazones (IV) and their characteristics

Sl. No.	R	m.p.°C		Molecular formula	Neutral Equivalent		Nitrogen%	
					Found	Required	Found	Required
1.	H	214-216	dec.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	300.00	296.32	9.22	9.46
2.	4-CH ₃	219-221	dec.	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	307.80	310.34	8.87	9.02
3.	2-OCH ₃	162-164	dec.	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	322.50	326.34	8.42	8.58
4.	4-OCH ₃	217-219	dec.	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄	328.00	326.34	8.46	8.58
5.	2-Cl	214-215	dec.	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₃	331.10	330.81	8.21	8.46
6.	3-Cl	221-223	dec.	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₃	326.70	330.81	8.18	8.46
7.	4-Cl	230-232	dec.	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₃	333.30	330.81	8.49	8.46

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s are uncorrected. UV spectra were obtained on a Bosch & Lomb Spectronic 600 model. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infra-cord, with sodium chloride optics.

4-Keto-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride phenylhydrazone: Aniline (0.92 g., 0.01 mole) was diazotized by treatment with hydrochloric acid (6 ml.), crushed ice (2 g.) and 20% aqueous sodium nitrite (4 ml.). The clear diazonium salt thus obtained was added dropwise to a solution of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride (2.18 g., 0.01 mole) in sodium carbonate (0.6 g. in 40 ml. water). The crude product precipitated immediately and was collected on a filter. Recrystallization of crude product from acetone afforded orange yellow crystalline solid (2.2 g., 69% yield), m.p. 203-205°. (Found N, 8.26. C₁₈H₁₄N₂O₄ requires N, 8.52%).

2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-3-carboxyl acrolein phenylhydrazone: A suspension of 4-keto-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconic anhydride phenylhydrazone in 8% aqueous sodium hydroxide (20 ml.) was refluxed until the solution became clear (2 hr.). An equal volume of water was added and the solution was filtered hot. The filtrate was extracted with ether to remove non-acidic impurities. Acidification of aqueous layer with dilute hydrochloric acid to persistent turbidity and subsequent chilling in ice resulted in a solid mass which was filtered, washed well with water and dried. Recrystallization of crude solid from absolute ethanol gave shining yellow crystals, m.p. 214-216° dec. (Found N, 9.22. C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₃ requires N, 9.46%).

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